

D2.2 Safety Guideline

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Deliverable Information sheet

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Executive summary

This deliverable includes:

- A summary of the MARBEL battery system parts/subsystems that are defined so far in the current state of the project together with a hazard analysis arising from the different parts/functions.
- A summary of the operational states the MARBEL battery system might be operated in during its lifetime.
- An identification of hazards categorized in electrical, mechanical and thermal/chemical.
- A definition of safety goals derived from the identified hazards including the description of how the hazards can be prevented. This includes the reaction of the involved subsystems/functions and the resulting safe state.

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List of abbreviations

<i>EV</i>	<i>Electric Vehicle</i>
<i>BP</i>	<i>Battery Pack</i>
<i>iSCM</i>	<i>Integrated Smart Cell Manager</i>
<i>CMC</i>	<i>Cell Management Controller</i>
<i>BMC</i>	<i>Battery Management Controller</i>
<i>BMS</i>	<i>Battery Management System</i>
<i>HV</i>	<i>High Voltage</i>
<i>UFC</i>	<i>Ultra-Fast Charging</i>
<i>ECU</i>	<i>Electronic Control Unit</i>
<i>OS</i>	<i>Operational State</i>
<i>sOS</i>	<i>Special Operational State</i>
<i>EMC</i>	<i>Electromagnetic Compatibility</i>

Introduction

The battery system developed in MARBEL will be a high-performance EV-battery, which will enable long distance trips, shorter recharging time and a high level of modularity at the same time. To reach these goals, different approaches and innovations will be performed. Some of these include high energy Li-Ion cells to be used in the system to store a high amount of energy. To reduce charging time and therefore enhance comfort for the driver, a novel ultra-fast charging strategy will be applied, resulting in high currents being applied to the system. Moreover, mechanical aspects will be improved, meaning new materials and design techniques will be used for a reduction of system weight, while ensuring a modular design that will later ease the process of dismantling or scaling the system according to the application. All these measures together will bring significant improvements to the system, but they require a thorough analysis of the system and its operational states to be always on track on how the system might and shall behave. For any interaction between humans and the MARBEL battery system, the safety of the involved parties is of utmost importance.

The objective of this deliverable therefore is to collect as thorough as possible any hazard that can arise from the different system parts the MARBEL battery system will consist of. Therefore, the complete system will be monitored with respect to operational states and behaviour. From these operational situations, possible hazards/malfunctions will be derived from the involved system entities, while a strong focus is on human safety. Thus, the highest goal is to take efforts to prevent those hazards from happening.

Moreover in this document, the intended behaviour of the involved system parts will be derived from the identified hazards together with a definition of the actions that need to be taken to prevent/mitigate the hazard and the resulting safe state. Wherever possible, limits in terms of physical values will be noted; however, not every limit is yet known in the current state of the project since some information/development is still ongoing or missing. The respective parts will be marked with a placeholder to emphasize that there sure is a physical limit, but the real value will be filled in later when available.

The main intention of this deliverable is to build a basic guideline and main reference for the developments in other work-packages when it comes to safety. It must be stated that at this time of the project the complete system architecture is not yet finalized, which on one hand increases the importance of main safety guidelines for aligning the developments in a later stage. On the other hand however, the hazards and safety goals defined in this document's version are based on the current knowledge of the general architecture and can therefore not deliver implementation details. The document shall thus be understood as first reference when defining the system architecture to include the main mechanisms and measures to ensure maximum safety for any human interacting with the MARBEL BP-system.

1. System parts of the MARBEL battery system

In this chapter, an overview of the MARBEL BP system parts and functions shall be given. Every subsystem – if applicable – will provide a set of required functionalities and/or devices that are obligatory to guarantee the safety of the MARBEL system, but most important the safety of every human interacting with it. A summary of these safety mechanisms is given in the “full-system”-section 1.7.

Figure 1: Draft - MARBEL BP system overview

The MARBEL BP consists of several sub-components; each of them is responsible for different safety mechanisms and functions that contribute to the safety of the full system. The energetic “heart” of the BP are the cells. They will be connected and arranged together to form the modules, which themselves will be again connected to each other to reach the desired level of high voltage and capacity. Monitoring multiple physical values like voltage, temperature and current, the iSCMs form the first communication point of cell-relevant data. They are connected wirelessly to the CMCs, which act as mediators between the iSCMs and the BMC, that completes the BMS of the pack. A cooling system will keep the cells temperatures within a desirable range, while taking commands from the BMS as well as communicating status values and other signals. The junction box / DC-box is responsible for safely activating the HV main interfaces; e.g. when a vehicle or a charging system shall be connected. Moreover, is it capable of changing the configuration inside the BP, so that different voltage levels can be achieved, depending on the system operation (e.g. charging vs. driving). To allow for a versatile and flexible connection of the MARBEL BP to any vehicle, the BMS will communicate its data to a Gateway, which will act as a mediator to connected systems and the rest-of-vehicle.

1.1. Li-Ion cells

The cells assembled in the MARBEL battery pack are high-energy pouch cells from the Chinese manufacturer CATL – Contemporary Amperex Technology Co. Ltd..

The following table gives a short overview of the main cell characteristics with a focus on safety relevance:

Table 1: Relevant parameters of the MARBEL BP cells by CATL

Item	Value	Description
Cell chemistry	Graphite / NMC-622	The cells consist of a graphite anode and an NMC-622 cathode. The mixture rate of cathode materials therefore is 60 % nickel, 20 % manganese and 20 % cobalt.
Cell capacity	C_{cell}	This is the rated capacity of the cells. It is related to a 1 C discharge. Since the value is not yet fixed, it is further referred to as C_{cell} .
Cell nominal voltage	U_{nom}	This is the nominal voltage of the cells. It is used for calculations such as power capability of the later battery system and for benchmarking. It is further referred to as U_{nom} .
Cell voltage limits (degradation)	$U_{max_degrade}$, $U_{min_degrade}$	These upper and lower voltage limits define the limits during operational use, meaning the cells shall not be operated outside of this voltage window to avoid accelerated aging. The values are further referred to as $U_{max_degrade}$ and $U_{min_degrade}$.
Cell voltage limits (safety)	U_{max_safety} , U_{min_safety}	These upper and lower voltage limits define the safety limits the cell must not exceed to avoid hazardous situations. The values are further referred to as U_{max_safety} and U_{min_safety} .
Cell temperature limits (degradation)	T_{max_degrad} , T_{min_degrad}	These upper and lower temperature limits are related to the degradation of the cells. To avoid accelerated aging, the cells should not be operated outside of this temperature window. The values are further referred to as T_{max_degrad} and T_{min_degrad} .
Cell temperature limits (safety)	T_{max_safety} , T_{min_safety}	These are the upper and lower temperature limits of the cells related to safety. To avoid hazardous events like thermal runaway or leaking, the cells must not be operated outside of this temperature window. The values are further referred to as T_{max_safety} and T_{min_safety} .
Cell current limit (degradation)	I_{max_degrad}	This limit specifies the maximum current allowed to avoid accelerated aging. It is defined in the cell

		datasheet and will further be referred to as L_max_degrad .
Cell current limit (safety)	L_max_safety	This limit specifies the maximum current allowed for safety reasons. Going above this limit must be prevented by the monitoring system of the MARBEL BP. This value is defined in the cell datasheet and will further be referred to as L_max_safety .

It shall be noted that the real physical values for the parameters marked in blue will be put in later when available. However, this does not change the character of any of the later defined safety goals.

1.2. Battery Modules

The battery modules within the pack will consist of multiple cells to form a modular unit. Inside the full pack, there will be n modules arranged in two banks, that can be connected either in series (for charging) or in parallel (for driving). Thus, the overall voltage of the MARBEL system will change during its operation, between 400 V and 800 V (given the status of system design at the time of creation of this deliverable). Together with busbars and other live connections the modules as compound will form the HV-system of the full pack.

Figure 2: Modules of MARBEL BP

The modules with their cells must be conditioned and monitored at any time of operation. Therefore, they are connected to the cooling system for thermal conditioning as well as to the BMS and the junction box for electrical conditioning/monitoring.

1.3. Cooling System

The cooling system or thermal management system consists of cooling fluid (water-glycol mixture) and a series of components that conduct the heat from cells to the cooling fluid. The thermal management system also heats-up the cells on cold ambient conditions or ultra-fast charging process.

The concept design of the thermal management system consists of possible integration of different cooling technologies. The considered technologies, e. g. stacks of heating pads, vapor chambers and coolant channels with aluminium foam on the top or bottom are shown in the next figure:

Figure 3: Pre-development concepts for battery cooling design

The vapor chamber transfers the heat from the cells to the top of the stack when the aluminium foam with the coolant fluid flows through and absorbs the heat. The coolant flows through each of the battery modules, absorbing the heat generated by the battery and is finally connected with the vehicle cooling system.

For the heat up of the battery the vehicle thermal system is responsible for providing a proper coolant inlet temperature. This warm up of the coolant can be realized via PTC heater and/or a heat pump functionality of the refrigerant circuit. Additionally, the heat up can be supported via heating pads placed between the cells. This causes a direct heat up of the cells.

1.4. DC-BOX / Junction box

The junction box together with the UFC-charging system will contribute to an overall safe operation of the system. It will consist of at least two main connectors that will activate the main HV-interfaces of the BP, but also of switches for changing the configuration of the modules inside the pack and to connect the battery-pack to the Engine. For that reason, the junction box will have a communication link to the BMS, from which it will receive commands for either activating or deactivating the system. It is therefore of utmost importance, that this device will be able to control the main connections reliably and safely to a vehicle or charging system. It is furthermore of high

interest to ensure the inherent safety of the system by ensuring open state of contactors if communication between parts is lost.

Figure 4: Sketch of the junction-box with its connections

The main task for the junction box is to make sure the battery module banks are connected properly and the desired configuration (e.g. for driving or charging) is present at the charging ports or the vehicle interface.

Obligatory functions to be implemented by the junction box:

- Hold the contactors to switch the configuration of the module banks
- Safely shut down the system by switching the contactors upon request (from BMS)
- Communicate with BMS during operation, charging and parking
- Safely maintaining the state of the contactors
- Open the contactors upon justified request (from BMS)
- Reliably communicate problems to the BMS
- Passively open the circuit in case of over-current by means of a fuse

Obligatory functions to be implemented by the DC-BOX:

- Control pilot manage /Proximity detection, to ensure proper connection to the EVSE and to send stop-charge signal in case of accidental disconnection
- PLC Communication with the EVSE
- Interlock: To block the connector to avoid accidental plug disconnection.

1.5. BMS

The BMS takes the role of the “main coordinator” amongst the subsystems of the MARBEL BP. It will act as master for the CMCs that are connected to the module banks and collect data from them to monitor the state of the cells at any time. Moreover, will it communicate with other components of the cooling system, the junction-box/charging system as well as the Gateway. The Gateway itself will not be a part of the BP, however, it plays an important role when it comes to securing the communication channel to the cloud. The following sketch shows the main components and interfaces of the BMS.

Figure 5: Components and interfaces of MARBEL BMS

The BMS consists of the BMC – the main ECU – and the CMCs, which are the communication masters for the iSCMs attached to the cells. More details about the architecture can be found in D4.2, where a complete architecture of the BMS is shown together with a functional safety analysis according to ISO26262.

Since the BMS will be a main communication knot for cell data, event-driven commands and the malfunction monitoring, it is highly important to define safety goals for its development and operation.

1.6. Housing concept / structure

Besides bringing innovation in terms of weight reduction and modularity, the housing of the MARBEL BP plays an important role when it comes to safety of the system. It will on one hand protect the inner parts like cells, cooling parts and ECUs from being damaged by mechanical impacts. On the other hand, it protects anyone who will interact with the system from touching live HV-parts. Thus, the housing of the BP will form a complete enclosure of all parts with defined interfaces for HV-connection as well as communication interfacing. Additionally, the housing with its conductive materials will be an active part in the electrical grounding system of the MARBEL BP. It must be mechanically strong, stable and durable to withstand the expected environmental conditions.

1.7. Full System

To reach a maximum of safety at the full system level, multiple main safety functions and subsystems must be included. They might be implemented or integrated in different places amongst the full system, however, as a complete compound, they must provide the safety functions as intended. Several regulations define main technical safety requirements and measures that electrical vehicles and their battery systems must provide.

A document released by SAE international in October 2020 - SAE-J2344 - defines "Guidelines for Electric Vehicle Safety" [1]. In the fourth chapter of the document, general guidelines defined from a vehicle point of view are defined besides multiple safety mechanisms/functions from the high voltage battery perspective. Other standards like the ISO6469 "Electrically propelled vehicles – safety specifications" (parts 1- 4), the UNECE R100, UN38.3, GB38031, ISO12405 and ISO17840 are also considered.

The complete system of MARBEL BP will include the following general safety functions and/or mechanisms (in accordance with [1-9]):

1.7.1. General Electrical Safety Guidelines

When operating a HV-battery system, one of the major threats persons are exposed to is suffering from electrical shock, or in general, hazards caused by high levels of voltage- or current. Therefore, MARBEL's BP will provide multiple mechanisms and functions to ensure no contact with live parts and to detect errors of isolation, that might be caused by different reasons (e.g. mechanical impact of the housing, degradation, etc.). These measures will include at least the following, but are not limited to these (if necessity of additional safety measures is detected as the MARBEL developments progress):

- **Measures for electrical isolation:** All electrically conductive parts must be isolated from the HV-live parts, both the negative and the positive ones (IT-System). Important factors shall be aligned with respective standards. The isolation resistance must be at least 100 Ω/V (applies to DC circuits). Clearance and creepage distance also have to be aligned with values from regulations, like the ISO6469. The isolation resistance will be monitored during system operation and measures taken if any abnormal behaviour is detected. All covers of live parts and other safety protections against electrical shock must not be removable without the help of tools. [1,2]
- **Automatic voltage disconnects device/functions in hazardous situations:** In case of an abnormal situation, this function will lead to a safe shutoff of any voltage leading parts (from the main connectors of the MARBEL BP to external circuit parts) without manual interaction. The trigger for such automatic disconnects can be manifold and are defined in a later stage, see section 4 (safety goals). This automatic voltage disconnect device will be formed by at least one main connector for each HV-bus (one for positive and one for negative).
- **Manual voltage disconnects:** There will be situations when the system must be maintained and/or other interaction with it is necessary. For such circumstances, it is extremely necessary to interrupt the HV-conductive output terminals manually and physically. By doing so, consequences of an unrequested or faulty switching of main connectors can be anticipated. This manual voltage disconnect device shall be located in a sensible place (easy to reach), only one of it shall be installed and the operation of it shall not require highly sophisticated expertise or special tools. [1] Situations, where such a manual disconnect will be necessary are sOS1-sOS6 (see next section).
- **General interlock functions:** An interrupt of HV-conducting parts must be detected and lead to an opening of the main contactors (trigger for the automatic voltage disconnect

device). Hence, every part that is removable and covering live parts and thus its removal induces access to HV-parts must be included in the interlock surveillance function. Moreover, the charging connector must also be included into the interlock function system to avoid hazardous voltages at such interfaces.

- **Grounding of the system:** The enclosure of the MARBEL BP must be able to connect to a vehicle conductive structure to ensure proper grounding. This must also be considered when a charging system is connected to the BP, which might have its own grounding and insulation monitoring.
- **HV-assemblies and -connectors:** Wires or connectors carrying HV-levels must be developed in accordance with respective regulations, e.g. SAE J1654, J1673 and J1742.
- **Fusing/short-circuit protection:** The electrical circuits will be secured by non-reversible fuses, meaning in case of damage caused by overcurrent this device(s) must be replaced after successfully eliminating the source of the problem.

1.7.2. Malfunction monitoring and signalling

To detect errors or abnormal situations inside the system, the MARBEL BP's ECUs will form a comprehensive surveillance system that keeps track of important signals and values as well as error monitoring. If an error is detected, a message will be stored in one of the ECUs for later investigations and the operator of the system will be notified (e.g. by a signal in a display). Depending on the severity of the malfunction, different actions will be taken (e.g. shutdown of the system).

1.7.3. Electromagnetic Compatibility

MARBEL's BP will be developed in accordance with EMC-regulations and tested according to DIN-EN61000-4-5. With that, it is ensured that the MARBEL BP will be operated safely also in noisy environments and during all operational states. Furthermore, shall the operation of the BP not lead to high electromagnetic emissions, that could disturb other nearby systems.

1.7.4. Labelling

When handling the battery pack of MARBEL, the interactor will be informed about the class B-HV-voltage level by a high voltage symbol according to IEC 60417 or symbol W012 in ISO7010.[9] This will be achieved by placing at least one of these labels on the top- and bottom side of the pack, so it can be identified easily and from either direction. The labelling can be extended to include more information, e.g. HV-level, capacity and/or cell chemistry. It is also possible to pack such information into a QR-code which can be read by a smartphone. However, the relevant information that the pack is a HV-system must be readable without the help of electronic devices. Wires that carry HV shall be coloured in orange. [1-4]

1.7.5. Single-Fault-Tolerance

The MARBEL BP shall be equipped with a certain level of redundancy in its fault monitoring system as well as automatic voltage disconnects to ensure reliable safety measures after a single failure occurred. An example for this is equipping the system with at least two main connectors, one for the positive and one for the negative HV-line, respectively.

1.7.6. Safety performance in operational environmental conditions

The MARBEL BP shall be developed and tested to perform safely during expectable environmental conditions that will be present during normal operation. This will include mechanical and thermal impacts/load due to e.g. driving in different locations. [2]

1.7.7. Comprehensive Testing campaign

To validate the safety of the system and to detect possible malfunctions, a comprehensive test campaign will be performed for all system parts; in partly assembled state over the full system to the testing in a vehicle environment. All testing activities will be documented and referred to the safety guidelines as well as to other defined requirements.

2. Operational states of the system

During its lifetime – which already begins at the manufacturing of sub-assemblies – the MARBEL BP can face different situations of operation. These are called “operational states”. Besides the obvious ones during regular use like parking, driving, charging etc., other situations with different safety threats arise. As an example, a car equipped with the MARBEL BP could be involved in an accident, which must be considered as “special operational state”, since it goes beyond the regular use of the BP and poses other and probably more dangerous risks. In the following, these states are briefly described with their main characteristics and the special risks they might pose to the driver and/or other interacting parties.

2.1. OS1 - Vehicle parking / no charging

In this state, multiple parts of the system can be active, depending on the time since the last driving operation. From a safety point of view, the surveillance functions of the system must be active, to avoid hazardous. Although there is little to less power demand from the system in OS1, external impacts can influence the system (e.g. thermal impact).

2.2. OS2 - Vehicle parking / (UFC) charging

During (ultra-fast) charging of the battery while parking, all system components are active and take part in the process. A special focus is on the charging-components/junction-box that will initiate the flow of high current into the battery. Additionally, the thermal management plays an important role in OS2, since the power flow into the battery is at a maximum. The connection to the charging system is also a factor, since another electrical system is connected to the BP, resulting in grounding considerations depending on the type of charging (AC, DC).

2.3. OS3 - Vehicle in normal operation / driving

This is the regular operational state where all parts of the system are active. While in other operational states the focus is often on a reliable and rather quick shutdown of the system (in case of abnormal situations), this is not necessarily the case in OS3. During driving, an unforeseen and hasty shutdown of the system can lead to serious accidents and must be avoided in any case.

2.4. sOS1 – System/System Parts in manufacturing process

This is a special operational case, since during manufacturing, the BP cannot be considered a functional and complete system. A special care must be taken, as live parts (cells, modules, busbars, connections etc.) can and will be uncovered during manufacturing process. Therefore, a high risk of electrical shock or causing short circuits is present. In addition, sharp edges of subcomponents that are usually not accessible in other operational states might lead to injuries of the involved workers. Strong focus must therefore be laid on safety clothing as well as special training of involved parties.

2.5. sOS2 – System/System Parts in Validation environment

The testing/validation is another operational state that poses high risks to involved parties. Since there are many situations where a malfunction of the system is provoked on purpose (including abusive situations), electrical as well as chemical and thermal risks arise. Therefore, the involved parties during testing must wear protective clothes all time, including gas masks when abusive tests or outcomes are expected. All parts of the system must be considered to prepare the situation of testing with a maximum focus on safety. Additionally, fire extinguishers as well as intensive training for behaving during abnormal test situations is highly necessary for all involved persons.

2.6. sOS3 - Vehicle in workshop / repair / maintenance

In this operational state, the battery system poses further risks to involved humans. It is somehow comparable to the sOS1, with the difference, that the battery system is not new anymore. In that case, it cannot be taken for granted that the state of the system is well-known. Furthermore, safety mechanisms and/or -functions might be deactivated on purpose, to perform maintenance or repair work. For that reason, safety measures comparable to sOS2 as well as sOS4 shall be considered. A high focus lies on training of involved workers, labelling the HV-system as well as documenting all performed modifications and work.

2.7. sOS4 - Vehicle involved in an accident

During an accident, important parts of the battery system could be damaged or be without function. For that reason, the BP must be able to react in an accident situation and immediately shutoff the HV-System, so that no external parts and components remain live. If the situation is that worse that the pack is mechanically damaged, objects intruded into the system or any other sort of physical damage happened, the intervention of involved rescue-forces must be supported in the best possible way. It is contributed to this by the HV-labelling of the system as well as proper shutdown attempt.

2.8. sOS5 – Recycling / Dismantling / 2nd-Life

When the MARBEL BP has reached its end-of-life, it is possible that it can further be used in a second-life application, be completely reused or just recycled. In any case, it can be necessary to evaluate the state of the system (e.g. for residual value assessment) or even dismantle it partly or completely. Thus, comparable safety considerations like in sOS1 – sOS3 are sensible. Especially when sOS5 is the consequent situation of sOS4, special care must be taken since parts of the system including cells could be in a dangerous state.

2.9. sOS6 – Transporting the system

Several reasons are possible that require a transport of the MARBEL BP during its lifetime. Be it either for transporting the system for test purposes to a lab facility after manufacturing or after an accident for the sake of recycling. In any case, a high focus is on ensuring the safety of the involved persons during the transport and a safe packaging as well as documentation of the transport. Regulations of the ADR/UNECE [5] must be followed to ensure a safe transportation.

3. Hazard Analysis

In any of the abovementioned operational states of the MARBEL BP, there might be potential hazardous situations that pose a threat to whoever is interacting with the system. The reasons for such dangerous happenings are manifold, from software failures over mechanical impacts to human failure while handling the system. In best case, all the hazards are identified and known, so that measures can be taken to prevent them from happening or mitigate the consequences.

The error-tree diagram in figure 7 shows the relations between several identified failure-modes (FM) and effects (E) resulting thereof. Depending on the operational state, the reasons for the failure modes as well as the effects can be various; they are mentioned in the grey boxes in figure 7. The causes are applicable to both the failure modes and the effects, since some effects can be directly provoked by different conditions (e.g. sOS2, external triggered overheating of a cell in an abusive test condition). It is important to understand relations and consequences of different FM and E, so that the severity of certain situations gets clear.

Below is an overview of the identified FM, E and causes.

Figure 6: Overview of identified failure modes (yellow), effects (red) and causes (grey)

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Figure 7: Relation between failure-modes and effects with possible causes

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As a consequence of the named failure-modes and effects, possible hazards are identified, categorized, and listed in the following. They should be defined as generic as possible; the link in terms of contingency measures to the respective subsystems will be then done in the “safety-goals”-section (section 4). For each hazard, some example situations are given to illustrate the link to the operational states.

3.1. Electrical Hazards

Table 2: Electrical Hazards

ID	Operational state	Hazard Description	Involved system parts
H-01	OS2,OS3, sOS1-sOS3, sOS5	<u>The system is being overcharged and thus the battery cells are charged to a higher voltage level than allowed by cell specifications.</u> OS2: charging system doesn't interrupt charge current after reaching the maximum charge voltage. OS3: recuperative charging is executed although charge level is too high. sOS1: system overcharged during end-of-line-tests. sOS2: system overcharged on purpose (e.g. shutoff test). sOS3: system overcharged after repair work. sOS5: 2 nd -Life application not using correct limit values.	Cells, charging system, BMS
H-02	all	<u>The system is being deep discharged and thus the battery cells are discharged to a lower voltage level than allowed by cell specifications.</u> All: in all the operational states this hazard could occur.	Cells, charging system, BMS
H-03	OS1,OS3, sOS1, sOS2-sOS6	<u>The system is discharged with a very low load and thus the battery cells are discharged with a current higher than allowed by cell specifications.</u> OS1: extensive isolation problem OS3: electrical fault in e.g. power electronics circuit sOS1: short circuit with some tools sOS2-sOS6: extensive isolation problem, short circuit with tools	Cells, junction-box, BMS
H-04	All	<u>The battery cells are short circuited and thus are discharged with a current exceeding the specification limit. (internal short circuit)</u> All: in all the operational states this hazard could occur.	Cells
H-05	All	<u>The battery system is being short circuited and thus the overall current exceeds the specified limits. In addition, system parts like busbars or connectors are heated up in a short period of time. (external short circuit)</u> All: in all the operational states this hazard could occur.	Cells, junction-box, BMS
H-06	OS2,OS3, sOS1- sOS3,	<u>The system is being charged at low temperatures (< 0 °C), thus the cells experience lithium plating which</u>	Cells,BMS,cooling-

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	sOS5	<p><u>might lead to short circuits and accelerated aging, thus reduced overall safety.</u></p> <p>OS2: cooling system fails to condition the cells to higher temperature. OS3: cooling system fails to condition the cells to higher temperature. sOS1-sOS3: e.g. cell conditioning fails or false conditioning on purpose sOS5: 2nd-life application has different environmental conditions</p>	system, charging-system
H-07	All	<p><u>Measurement of physical values like voltage, current or temperature is non-functional or non-plausible, e.g. due to sensor failure.</u></p> <p>All: in all the operational states this hazard could occur.</p>	BMS, junction-box, cooling system, charging system
H-08	All	<p><u>Shutdown of the system is not working properly, thus no electrical disconnection to other non-battery parts is possible.</u></p> <p>All: in all the operational states this hazard could occur.</p>	Junction-box, BMS, charging system
H-09	All	<p><u>A main contactor of the system is defective and thus cannot be closed.</u></p> <p>All: in all the operational states this hazard could occur.</p>	Junction-box, BMS, charging system
H-10	All	<p><u>A main contactor of the system is defective or welded (e.g. due to a previous overcurrent event) and thus cannot be opened.</u></p> <p>All: in all the operational states this hazard could occur.</p>	Junction-box, BMS, charging system
H-11	OS1, OS2, sOS2, sOS3, sOS5	<p><u>High current flow between two battery-parts while connecting them in parallel due to an imbalance of the voltage levels.</u></p> <p>OS1: unintended switching of configuration leads to high equalizing current. OS2: switching is executed before voltages are equalized. sOS2: switching in unequalized state is done on purpose. sOS3: unintended switching of configuration leads to high equalizing current. sOS5: unintended switching of configuration leads to high equalizing current.</p>	Cells, junction-box, BMS
H-12	sOS5	<p><u>The BMS fails to correctly switch from 1st-Life to 2nd-Life application and thus operates at wrong physical value limits.</u></p> <p>sOS5: transition to 2nd-Life not working properly.</p>	Cells, BMS
H-13	sOS1-sOS6	<p><u>Electrical components are exposed or not covered properly and thus can be touched (> 60 VDC).</u></p> <p>sOS1-sOS6: whenever interacting with the system in terms of repair, testing, manufacturing, dismantling, transportation or when it's involved in an accident, regularly covered parts of the system could be exposed.</p>	All live parts
H-14	All	<p><u>Electrical isolation surveillance is not functional and thus no information about the isolation resistance can be derived.</u></p>	BMS, junction-box, charging-

		All: in all the operational states this hazard could occur.	system, DC-Box
H-15	All	<u>Electrical isolation is interrupted and thus no proper isolation resistance is reached.</u> All: in all the operational states this hazard could occur.	BMS, junction-box, charging-system, DC-Box
H-16	All	<u>Occurrence of an electric arc due to failures in e.g. the charging system or due to mechanical deformation.</u> All: in all the operational states this hazard could occur.	pack, charging-system
H-17	All	<u>The state of the system is unclear, due to non-functional communication link to the BMS and/or non-functional electrical connection to the system.</u> All: in all the operational states this hazard could occur.	Full system
H-18	sOS1-sOS6	<u>No handling-recommendation for non-normal situations (e.g. accident, testing etc.) is defined and thus no training prerequisites can be defined and handling the system is risky for involved parties.</u> sOS1-sOS6: in all special operational states thorough handling recommendation could be missing and thus e.g. no training of personnel or workflow preparation possible.	/
H-19	OS1-OS3	<u>System is vulnerable because of exposed data channels.</u> OS1-OS3: when connected to the cloud for data exchange, attackers could inject malicious data frames.	BMS, junction-box, charging-system, cooling system, Gateway
H-20	sOS1-sOS6	<u>The system is mechanically deformed and thus the cells might be short circuited or damaged otherwise.</u> sOS1-sOS6: e.g. crash, damage during repair/manufacturing/validation	Full system

3.2. Mechanical Hazards

Table 3: Mechanical Hazards

ID	Operational state	Hazard Description	Involved system parts
H-21	sOS1-sOS6	<u>The system's housing has sharp edges or parts that are not covered and thus exposed to any involved party.</u> sOS1-sOS6: In all of these states the system might not be covered by a vehicle structure, so interaction will be closer with higher risk of contact.	BP-housing
H-22	sOS1-sOS6	<u>Subassembly parts inside the housing might have sharp edges that are not covered and thus can be touched.</u> sOS1-sOS6: The system might be partly assembled or opened, so work inside the BP or with subassemblies is possible.	Full system

H-23	All	<u>Parts of the system are loosening due to corrosion or material failure/fatigue.</u> All: in all operational states reasons for loosening parts can occur.	Full system
H-24	sOS1-sOS6	<u>Parts of the system are not fixed properly and thus can move inside the housing and damage further parts.</u> sOS1-sOS6: In all of these states parts could be unfastened, e.g. by not properly fixing after repair-work or due to an accident.	Full system
H-25	sOS1-sOS6	<u>The system has a high weight and thus poses a risk during handling.</u> sOS1-sOS6: Whenever the BP is maneuvered for different reasons (transport, repair, validation, etc.), the weight of the system poses a risk.	Full system

3.3. Thermal and Chemical Hazards

Table 4: Thermal and Chemical Hazards

ID	Operational state	Hazard Description	Involved system parts
H-26	OS1 OS2, OS3, sOS1, sOS2, sOS3, sOS4,	<u>The system or cells within the system catch fire.</u> OS1: Vehicle parked under the sun, high environmental temperature. OS2. If the cooling system is not able to evacuate the heat generated. OS3. High PWT loads could lead to heating up the battery too much. SOS1. Creating a short-circuit during the assembly process. SOS2. Creating a short-circuit during the validation (at workshop), the cooling system is not operating properly, or the cooling system is not connected to a proper coolant source. SOS3. Creating a short-circuit SOS4. Short circuit due to component damage.	Cell, Module, Battery pack, Cooling system
H-27	sOS4	<u>Cells within the system vent and thus releasing possible toxic gasses/smoke/electrolyte.</u> SOS4. Component damage due to accident.	Cell, Module, Battery pack, Cooling system
H-28	OS1 OS2, OS3,	<u>Cells/system parts are operated at an elevated temperature > $T_{max\ degrad}$ °C (relevant for degradation).</u> OS1: Vehicle parked under the sun, high environmental temperature. OS2. If the cooling system is not able to evacuate the heat generated. OS3. High PWT loads could lead to heating up the battery too much.	Cell,
H-29	OS1	<u>Cells/system parts are operated at critical temperatures > $T_{max\ safety}$ °C (relevant for safety)</u>	Cell, Module, Battery pack,

	OS2, OS3,	OS1: Vehicle parked under the sun, high environmental temperature OS2. If the cooling system is not able to evacuate the heat generated. OS3. High PWT loads could lead to heating up the battery too much.	
H-30	sOS1, sOS2, sOS3, sOS4,	<u>A single cell inside the system overheats, enters thermal runaway and propagates to surrounding cells/system parts.</u> SOS1. Creating a short-circuit during the assembly process. SOS2. Creating a short-circuit during the validation (at workshop), the cooling system is not operating properly, or the cooling system is not connected to a proper coolant source. SOS3. Creating a short-circuit SOS4. Short circuit due to component damage.	Cell, Module, Battery pack, Cooling system
H-31	sOS2, SOS3, sOS4,	<u>Coolants or other fluids from system parts (e.g. cooling system) leak and are released to the in- or outside of the housing.</u> SOS2. The setup of the test bench is not properly done. Connections losing refrigerant. SOS3. The repair of the cooling system is not properly done. First, all coolant shall be evacuated before any disassembly. SOS4. Damage to the plates or connections could lead to leakage.	Cell, Module, Battery pack, Cooling system
H-32	sOS1- sOS6	<u>System parts related to the cooling might carry hot coolant and might be touched by involved parties.</u> The coolant will not be higher than 60-70°C. In theory, all components shall be able to operate at such temperatures, including electronics components. However, during repair or maintenance work or in other special situations, hot coolant could lead to injury/scalding of interacting persons.	-

4. Safety Goals

In this chapter, safety goals derived from the identified hazards and related to the different system parts are defined. They describe what (hazardous) situations shall be avoided together with a technical description on how this shall be done. As mentioned earlier, these safety goals are mainly decoupled from concrete implementation details at the level of each respective subsystem, since this will be done in a later stage when the architecture definition is done, for which the herein defined goals form the main base. Where applicable, a safe state is defined, into which the system is transitioned in case of the named situations.

The tables are arranged in the following manner:

- **ID:** The ID uniquely identifies the safety goals to refer to it wherever possible (e.g. during test definition). The IDs syntax is as follows: **SG-abbreviation-index**
 - **SG:** “Safety Goal”
 - **abbreviation:** [C: “cell” | TM: “thermal management” | BMS: “BMS” | JCH: “junction-box/charging” | MH: “materials/housing” | CYB: “cyber-security” | ROH: “rest-of-vehicle” | VAL: “validation”]
 - **index:** increasing counter
- **Related hazard:** a reference to the abovementioned hazards
- **Description:** what goal shall be achieved
- **Technical measure:** how shall the goal be achieved
- **Safe state:** what is the result of the mitigation of the hazardous situation

4.1. Safety Goals for Cell Operation

Table 5: Safety Goals for Cell Operation

ID	Related Hazard	Description	Technical measure	Safe State
SG-C-01	H-01, H-02, H-12	A cell in the system must not be operated outside a voltage level of $[U_{min_safety}, U_{max_safety}]$ V.	A control unit (e.g. BMS) shall prevent the cell from being charged/discharged beyond the voltage limits by a hard interrupt of the charging/discharging procedure (e.g. contactor opening).	Any sort of charging/discharging is not possible (contactors open).
SG-C-02	H-06, H-26, H-28, H-29, H-30	A cell in the system must not be operated outside a temperature range of $[T_{min_safety}, T_{max_safety}]$ °C.	A control unit (e.g. BMS) shall prevent the cell from being operated outside of the critical temperature range by a hard interrupt of the charging/discharging procedure (e.g. contactor opening).	Any sort of charging/discharging is not possible (contactors open).
SG-C-03	H-03, H-04, H-05, H-11, H-12, H-27	The maximum allowed current I_{max_safety} the cell can handle at a respective operating point must be followed.	A control unit (e.g. BMS) shall limit the current flow if the maximum limit is exceeded by a hard interrupt (e.g. contactor opening).	Any sort of charging/discharging is not possible (contactors open).
SG-C-04	H-20, H-26, H-27, H-31	Any cell used in the system must be protected against mechanical impacts like compression or deformation.	The design of the the battery pack (and its respective modules) must ensure a safe packing of cells with an adequate protection against mechanical impacts during the operation of the system.	Cell not deformed or otherwise mechanically stressed by normal operating conditions.

4.2. Safety Goals for Thermal Management

Table 6: Safety Goals for Thermal Management

ID	Related Hazard	Description	Technical measure	Safe State
SG-TM-01	H-20 H-26 H-27 H-31	Damage to components (cells, cooling system) due to accident shall be avoided/mitigated.	Reinforced structure	None (passive measure)
SG-TM-02	H-03 H-04 H-05	Accidental short circuit during assembly, maintenance shall be avoided.	Asymmetric design (only one possible assembly position)	None (passive measure)
SG-TM-03	H-06 H-26 H-28 H-29 H-30	Overheating while parked during hot ambient shall be avoided.	Stand-by cooling operation. Integrate temperature sensors, and a specific strategy. Integration of temperature sensors + temperature monitoring.	Coolant temperature < <u>T_{max_degrad}</u> Coolant temperature < <u>T_{max_safety}</u>
SG-TM-04	H-06 H-26 H-28 H-29 H-30	Overheating while Ultra-fast charging shall be avoided.	Ultrafast charging cut-off. Integration of temperature sensors + temperature monitoring.	Coolant temperature < <u>T_{max_degrad}</u> Coolant temperature < <u>T_{max_safety}</u> Cut-off UFC process.
SG-TM-05	H-06 H-26 H-28 H-29 H-30	Overheating while normal operation shall be avoided.	Set the cooling system at max performance. Progressive power limitation to the PWT.	Coolant temperature < <u>T_{max_degrad}</u> Electric load to the PWT limited
SG-TM-06	H-31	Coolant leakage during maintenance, or validation shall be avoided.	Define instructions for performing validation and maintenance operations.	None (passive measure)
SG-TM-07	H-31	Frozen coolant must be avoided since it damages the cooling channels or structures.	Choose coolant composition suitable for low temperatures.	None (passive measure)
SG-TM-08	H-31	Leakage of coolant into the module/cell shall be detected.	Coolant level sensor	Min. coolant level – reduce power output, shut down drivetrain
SG-TM-09	H-29 H-30	Thermal runaway of one cell and	Passive coolant circulation	Drive train shut down

		thermal propagation shall be avoided.		
SG-TM-10	H-31	Corrosion of the cooling channels shall be avoided.	Avoid condensed water in the Battery pack and corrosion inhibitor in the coolant	None (passive measure)

4.3. Safety Goals for BMS

In this part the main safety goals for the operation of a developed BMS are described. However, there is another deliverable dealing with the functional safety of the BMS (D4.2). These safety goals shall be referenced to the D4.2 to complete this general view with more implementation details.

Table 7: Safety Goals for BMS

ID	Related Hazard	Description	Technical measure	Safe State
SG-BMS-01	/	Any shutoff necessity that is triggered by the safety limitations of the cells must not lead to a hazardous event for any involved party (e.g. driver).	A control unit (e.g. BMS) must observe all safety limits of the cells and anticipate overshooting the limits in order to initiate contingency measures with a minimum impact for the operating situation of the system. A sudden and unannounced shutoff of the system must be prevented in any case.	Overshooting of safety cell limits prevented. A sudden shutoff of the system is not allowed.
SG-BMS-02	H-01 H-02 H-12	A cell in the system shall not be operated outside a voltage level of $[U_{min_degrade}, U_{max_degrade}]$ V to avoid cell degradation.	A control unit (e.g. BMS) shall limit the charge/discharge by observing the cell voltages and communicating the requested stop of charging/discharging to other system parts.	Charging/Discharging is not allowed until the cell voltage is within the allowed voltage window.
SG-BMS-03	H-06 H-26 H-28 H-29 H-30	Cells shall not be operated outside a temperature window of $[T_{min_degrade}, T_{max_degrade}]$ °C to avoid cell degradation.	A BMS shall be developed to observe the cell temperatures and communicate a stop request for charging/discharging to other involved system parts.	Charging/discharging is only allowed within the temperature window.
SG-BMS-04	H-03 H-04 H-05 H-11 H-12 H-27	Cells shall not be operated above a current limit of $[L_{max_degrade}]$ A to avoid cell degradation.	A BMS shall immediately send a shutdown request to the junction box to interrupt the operation of the system.	Defective CMC or power control from Powertrain
SG-BMS-05	H-06	The charging current of cells shall be limited when operating at low temperatures.	A BMS shall observe cell temperatures and limit the charging current for negative temperatures.	Charging not allowed / allowed with low current at negative temperatures.
SG-BMS-06	H-03 H-04 H-05 H-11 H-12 H-27	The maximum allowed current defined by peripherals (busbars, wiring etc.) must not be exceeded.	A control unit (e.g. BMS) shall limit the current flow if the maximum limit is exceeded. It must also take into account limits that are driven by the dimensioning of peripherals.	Charging/Discharging is not allowed as long as the current is not reduced to an allowable level.

SG-BMS-07	H-17 H-12	The BMS shall be able to store extraordinary events.	A BMS shall hold storage for event registration for later investigation.	/
SG-BMS-08	H-08	A loss of sensor values (temperature, voltage, current) shall not lead to a shutdown of the system if the time of loss is $< T_{max_loss}$	A BMS shall compensate the loss of the sensor value by means of software mitigation measures and store an error message in its event storage.	The loss of sensor signal does not have any effect except a notification for the user.
SG-BMS-09	H-07 H-08	A defective sensor (temperature, voltage, current) shall be detected.	A BMS shall have the possibility to detect a defective sensor and shall initiate an event storage entry as well as a safe shutdown of the system. The user shall be notified (e.g. display message).	Defective sensor detected. No charging/discharging possible.
SG-BMS-10	H-07 H-08 H-17	A defective wiring in communication lines shall be detected.	A BMS shall regularly check the physical state of wirings (e.g. before startup) and be able to detect faulty behavior.	Defective wiring/communication detected. No charging/discharging possible.
SG-BMS-11	H-07 H-08 H-17	A defective CMC shall not lead to a hazardous event.	A BMS shall immediately send a shutdown request to the junction box to interrupt the operation of the system. An event storage entry as well as a user notification shall be initiated. A sort of emergency run program shall be initiated.	Defective CMC detected. No charging/discharging possible.
SG-BMS-12	H-09 H-14 H-15	Electrical shock due to unrequested closing of main contactors must be avoided.	A BMS shall monitor and/or request the state of the contactors from the junction-box and prevent configurations that lead to electrical shock.	Incorrect contactor maneuver prevented.
SG-BMS-13	H-07 H-08 H-17	An unresponsive or offline behavior of the main ECU (BMS) must be detected and corrected if existent.	A watchdog subroutine shall restart the software if non-responsive BMS is detected.	Non-functional BMS due to e.g. Software bug or excessive EMI is detected and corrected. No impact on system operation.

4.4. Safety Goals for Charging System/DC-Box/Junction Box

Table 8: Safety Goals for Charging System / DC-Box / Junction Box

ID	Related Hazard	Description	Technical measure	Safe State
SG-JCH-01	H-01	One defective main contactor shall not have impact on the ability to shut down the system.	The junction box shall have at least two main contactors for the purpose of disconnecting the main high-voltage interface of the pack.	System will be shut down. No charging/discharging possible while main contactor defective.
SG-JCH-02	H-08 H-09 H-10	A defective main contactor shall be detected.	The junction box shall be able to detect the state of a main contactor and communicate it to the BMS.	Defective main contactor detected. No charging/discharging

				possible while main contactor defective.
SG-JCH-03	H-03 H-11	Switching from serial to parallel configuration with unbalanced voltages of the module banks must be avoided.	The junction box shall monitor the module bank voltages and communicate the values to the BMS. A switching shall be refused if necessary.	No operation of the system possible.
SG-JCH-04	H-08	Unrequested closing of contactors must be avoided.	The junction box shall continuously monitor the state of the contactors.	Contactors will be opened.
SG-JCH-05	H-08	Unrequested opening of contactors must be avoided.	The junction box shall validate the states of the contactors.	Integrity of HV-system ensured.
SG-JCH-06	H-07 H-08	Defective sensors must be detected (if not done by another ECU, e.g. BMS).	The junction box shall be able to detect malfunction of its sensors and communicate the result to the BMS. A check of the sensors must be done regularly and in addition always before startup of the system.	Defective sensors detected. Result communicated to BMS to trigger action / action triggered by junction box.
SG-JCH-07	H-14 H-15	Electrical isolation must be monitored continuously to detect isolation problems.	The junction box shall cooperate with the BMS in terms of regular isolation measurement. Detected errors must be immediately reported.	Isolation problems detected.
SG-JCH-08	H-03, H-04, H-05, H-11, H-12, H-27	An excessive overcurrent event shall be interrupted in any case.	In case of an overcurrent situation and an additional non-functional voltage shutdown system (e.g. contactors), fuses shall form a safe current interruption device.	Overcurrent interrupted.
SG-JCH-09	H-13 H-16	Energy stored in intermediate circuits must be properly charged and discharged.	A precharge circuit for vehicle-power-electronic connection must be equipped. In case of abnormal situations and at every system shutdown, the energy stored in the intermediate circuit must be safely discharged within a period of time defined in the system design phase.	Energy in intermediate circuit safely controlled.

4.5. Safety Goals for Materials/Housing Construction

Table 9: Safety Goals for Materials / Housing Construction

ID	Related Hazard	Description	Technical measure	Safe State
SG-MH-01	H-01	The housing of the system must completely enclose the modules and peripherals needed inside the pack.	A housing that protects the inner parts (cells, cooling plates etc.) from mechanical damage as well as individuals getting in contact with live parts shall be constructed.	No possibility to touch live parts.

SG-MH-02	H-27 H-31	Leakage of chemicals to the outside of the housing shall be avoided.	A housing that is completely closed shall be developed.	No leakage of liquid chemicals possible.
SG-MH-03	H-14 H-15 H-23	Water intrusion into the housing shall be avoided.	A housing that can withstand water contact shall be developed according to IPx6-IPx7, depending on operation conditions.	No water intrusion possible.
SG-MH-04	H-14 H-15	The housing with its conductive parts must contribute to a reliable detection of insulation errors.	An insulation monitoring function must be implemented in cooperation with the BMS to identify problems in electrical isolation.	Isolation errors detected.

4.6. Cybersecurity Goals for Data exchange/communication

Table 10: Cybersecurity Goals for Data exchange / communication

ID	Related Hazard	Description	Technical measure	Safe State
SG-CYB-01	H-19	An unauthorized injection of data shall not be possible.	The system shall detect the unauthorized injection of data into the communication between the backend and the battery pack. The system shall delete injected data.	Reject malicious messages
SG-CYB-02	H-19	An unauthorized replay of legitimated data shall not impact system's operation.	The system shall ignore replayed legitimate data.	Reject malicious messages
SG-CYB-03	H-19	Data shall be protected from unauthorized modification.	The system shall protect integrity of the communication channel. The system should detect modified data and delete it.	Data can't be altered from unauthorized actors
SG-CYB-04	H-19	On request, secure identities shall be available for communication.	Communication shall offer authentication using secure identities on request. Regarding the communication pattern, either client, server, or both communication partners authenticate themselves.	Every participant in a communication can be authenticated if requested by communication peer.
SG-CYB-05	H-19	Communication of data shall be confidential.	The system shall protect the confidentiality of communication data if requested by communication endpoints	No unauthorized data access possible

4.7. Safety Goals from the vehicle perspective (“rest-of-vehicle”)

Table 11: Safety Goals from the vehicle perspective

ID	Related Hazard	Description	Technical measure	Safe State
SG-ROH-01	H-13 H-14 H-15 H-16	The battery pack shall be an IT system.	No part of the system that has a galvanic connection to the cells shall have a connection to the housing of the system.	No galvanic connection between high voltage parts and the housing.
SG-ROH-02	H-08 H-09 H-10 H-16 H-17 H-18	A reliable physical disconnect of the main high voltage interface must be possible in addition to the main contactors.	The system shall have a manual switch (“Service-Disconnect”) that physically and viewably interrupts the main high voltage interface.	System not operational. Charge/Discharge not allowed. No voltage at the main HV-contactors.
SG-ROH-03	H-08	Live connectors must be avoided when any connection to the vehicle is interrupted.	The battery system must monitor the state of all external connections at any time to detect any interrupt that must be followed by an opening of main contactors.	Live connectors while interrupted connections not possible.
SG-ROH-04	H-08 H-17	The battery system must be able to communicate relevant data to other non-battery-ECUs in the vehicle environment.	An external data channel shall be considered to communicate data to the rest-of-vehicle.	Communication between non-battery-ECUs and battery-ECUs possible.
SG-ROH-05	H-08	The battery system must have a pilot-line function, so that disconnecting any HV-part outside of the BP will lead to an opening of main contactors.	All HV-leading parts are connected with an active signal line which will be interrupted when disconnecting a plug, wire or other assemblies.	Opening of contactors, no HV at the main vehicle interface.
SG-ROH-06	H-07 H-08	Communication errors between ECUs must not lead to a hazardous system failure or any other unwanted behavior.	Data exchange between ECUs involved in system operation must be validated by means of communication protocol to detect communication errors. Communication problems must be reported as well as corrected to ensure a proper data exchange.	Communication problems have no impact on system safety. Errors are reported and mitigation measures taken by involved ECUs.

4.8. Safety Goals from Validation perspective

Table 12: Safety Goals from Validation perspective

ID	Related Hazard	Description	Technical measure	Safe State
SG-VAL-01	All	Injury of any individual involved in testing shall be avoided.	Protective clothing must be worn: protective goggles, protective clothes, safety shoes. No jewellery worn during the tests. Personnel involved in testing must be trained. Break-times must be followed. Special equipment (fire extinguisher etc.) must be carried. Any testing area must be delimited, to lock it from entrance by any unauthorized person. It must moreover be highlighted as testing area in accordance with the highlighting of the HV-system. If the testing area contains large machines and/or other dangerous equipment like rotating parts, the area must further be physically locked /and or separated to completely avoid access by unauthorized personnel.	/
SG-VAL-02	All	Transportation guidelines must be followed.	System must be packed into packaging according to the regulations of ADR. The main contactors must be covered with isolating material. The service-disconnect must be disconnected during transport. Documentation of the transport must be provided including a detailed and understandable description of the device under transport. The same applies for all transportation activities of any subassemblies, cells or other subcomponents.	System not operational. Charge/Discharge not allowed. No voltage at the main HV-contactors.
SG-VAL-03	All	Documentation of every performed test must be thoroughly done.	Every test will be recorded with conditions, special observations, timings, dates, persons present during testing, location, test equipment. A detailed listing of documentation content will be done in WP7.	/
SG-VAL-04	All	Safety functions of the developed BMS must be validated.	The correct surveillance of critical parameters and the intended behavior in case of approaching the limits must be tested. This will include test such as but not limited to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Voltage limits 	BMS-safety surveillance functions approved.

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Current limits • Temperature limits • Pilot-line function <p>The detailed description of the necessary tests together with the test conditions, prerequisites, expected outcome and recorded data will be delivered in D7.1 in WP7 (testing and validation)</p>	
SG-VAL-05	All	Effects of non-functional sensors/CMCs/iSCMs/ECUs must be validated.	<p>The behaviour of non-functional sub-parts of the system must be validated. This will include tests such as but not limited to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Operating the system with unplugged sensor(s) • Disconnecting the power supply from ECUs/iSCMs/CMCs during operation <p>The detailed description of the necessary tests together with the test conditions, prerequisites, expected outcome and recorded data will be delivered in D7.1 in WP7 (testing and validation)</p>	HV-system-integrity approved.
SG-VAL-06	All	Effects of physical communication/power line problems must be validated.	<p>The behaviour of the system in case of physical errors must be validated. This will include tests such as but not limited to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Disconnecting communication wires/power connection wires • Short circuiting wires • High contact resistance of communication/power connection wires <p>The detailed description of the necessary tests together with the test conditions, prerequisites, expected outcome and recorded data will be delivered in D7.1 in WP7 (testing and validation)</p>	HV-system-integrity approved.
SG-VAL-07	All	Effects of EMC impacts on the system must be validated.	<p>EMC testing in different environmental conditions must be executed to study the system's behaviour in noisy environments and possible noise emitted from the system. The detailed description of the necessary tests together with the test conditions, prerequisites, expected outcome and recorded data will be delivered in D7.1 in WP7 (testing and validation)</p>	EMC-compatibility approved.

SG-VAL-08	All	The performance of the MARBEL battery system must be validated.	<p>Performance of the system must be validated by a comprehensive test campaign. This will include tests such as but not limited to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Charge/discharge at different rates • OCV-curve • Power-capability • Pulse-power tests • Internal resistance tests • HPPC profile • Driving profiles (e.g. WLTC) • Cold-cranking • Energy efficiency • Capacity validation • SoC calculation • SoH calculation <p>The detailed description of the necessary tests together with the test conditions, prerequisites, expected outcome and recorded data will be delivered in D7.1 in WP7 (testing and validation)</p>	Performance-related behaviour approved.
SG-VAL-09	All	The behaviour of the system under abusive and non-normal conditions must be validated.	<p>Under provoked abusive conditions or non-normal operation of the system, the behaviour must be studied. This will include tests such as but not limited to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overcharge • Deep discharge • Short circuit • Fuel fire test • Nail penetration • Crush • Shock/vibration • Thermal propagation test according to GB38031 <p>The detailed description of the necessary tests together with the test conditions, prerequisites, expected outcome and recorded data will be delivered in D7.1 in WP7 (testing and validation)</p>	Abuse behaviour validated.
SG-VAL-10	All	Common and latest standards shall be considered when planning the validation campaign to get a comprehensive test result.	<p>Standards like the following (not limited to the following) shall be considered for test planning:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UN38.3 • UNECE R100 • IEC62281 • IEC62660-2 • IEC62660-3 • IEC TR 62660-4 • ISO12405-parts 1-4 • SAND2005-3123 	/

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SAEJ1766 • SAEJ1798 • SAEJ2344 • ISO16750-3 • GB38031 	
SG-VAL-11	All	Limits for test execution must be thoroughly adjusted and rechecked for any test equipment.	When testing the system, the voltage, temperature and current limits must be set in accordance with the specified values. This applies to all tests where no abusive condition is provoked. In any case, a thorough documentation of the adjusted limits and used safety shutdown measures of the test equipment must be maintained together with the (sub-)system's limits.	System parameter limits not exceeded by test equipment.
SG-VAL-12	All, especially H-18	A comprehensive and detailed documentation about the safety relevant topics when interacting with the MARBEL BP must be created to act as a reference for different purposes (e.g. training of repair workers, deriving handling recommendations for rescue forces etc.).	The documentation will be a report that will cover the main parts of the MARBEL battery system together with main safety related parameters. Handling recommendations as well as special risks must be highlighted. The document shall act as basis for further training about the system. The special operational states (sOS1-sOS6) shall be especially focussed.	/

5. Conclusion

In this document, a comprehensive analysis of safety relevant concerns within and around the MARBEL battery system was performed. For that reason, the several system parts were described together with their main (safety) functions and their interaction to form the full system. To cover as much circumstances as possible in which the MARBEL BP can be operated during its lifetime, several operational states and special operational states were described. In each of them, special threats and risks were identified, to form a proper base for the performed hazard analysis. For this analysis, possible failure modes, effects and causes were collected and studied to build a comprehensive set of hazards. To prevent those hazards from arising, multiple safety goals associated with the different subsystems of the MARBEL BP were defined.

The number of safety goals and hazards makes clear, that high effort needs to be spent into the development of a safe system. Since the architecture of the BP is not yet finished at this time, this document must be repeatedly considered and maintained during the stages of further and more detailed design. As more details arise, a clearer view for planning safety measures will be developed.

As a consequence, the character of this document “D2.2 Safety Guideline” becomes clear: a basic and initial but ever “living” document to consider and refer to when detailing, defining and developing system parts in the different work-packages. The herein defined safety goals and -measures shall be main safety pillars. This will contribute to reach the highest goal in the development: ensuring a safe and reliable operation, performance and interaction with the MARBEL BP for any involved human.

6. REFERENCES

- [1] *Guidelines for Electric Vehicle Safety*, SAEJ2344, 2020.
- [2] *Electrically propelled road vehicles - Safety specifications*, ISO6469-1, 2019.
- [3] *Road vehicles - Information for first and second responders*, ISO17840-4, 2018.
- [4] *Regulation No. 100 - Uniform provisions concerning the approval of vehicles with regards to specific requirements for the electric power train*, UN/ECE R100, 2013
- [5] *UN Recommendations on the Transport of Dangerous Goods*, ADR, 2019.
- [6] *UN Manual of Tests and Criteria*, UN38.3_r7, 2019.
- [7] *Electrically propelled road vehicles - Test specification for lithium-ion traction battery packs and systems*, ISO12405, 2018.
- [8] *Electric Vehicles Traction Battery Safety Requirements*, GB38031-2020, 2020.
- [9] *Graphical symbols - Safety colours and safety signs - Registered safety signs*, ISO7010:2019, 2019.